

paper Chain

Recycling analysis of the end-of-life of
developed products

D4.3

May 2019 (M24)

Author:

V. M. Ferreira., M. Morais, H. Paiva, F. Simões (UAVR),

WP4, Task 4.3

New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

Deliverable No.	4.3
Dissemination level	Public
Work Package	4 Pre industrial Scale demonstration of the circular value chain
Task	4.3 Recycling potential analysis
Lead beneficiary	18. Universidade de Aveiro (UAVR)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	ACCIONA, SP, UPC, ZAG
Due date of deliverable	31 May 2019
Actual submission date	10 November 2020 (second submission)

Document history

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1	12/04/2019	UAVR	Victor Ferreira, Miguel Morais, H. Paiva, F. Simões
2		ZAG	Karmen Fifer Bizjak
3		Acciona Construction S.A.	Juan José Cepriá, Anurag Bansal, Antonio Martinez Puche
4		SP Processum	Gunnar Westin, Marie-Louise Wallberg
5	09/11/2020	UAVR	Victor Ferreira, Miguel Morais, H. Paiva, F. Simões
FV	10/11/2020	Acciona Construction S.A.	Juan José Cepriá

0 Executive Summary

Task 4.3 “Recycling potential analysis” is the last task of the work package WP4 of the PAPERCHAIN project. This WP4 aims to anticipate constraints and performing the assessment of the recycling potential of the developed solutions. The objectives of this deliverable 4.3 are the following:

- Analyze the end-of-use recycling alternatives for the developed solutions
- Close the end of life of the new circular solutions
- Recommendations for managing the end of life of the developed products
- Discuss recyclability potential of new solutions and recommendations for managing the end of life of the new developed products

Society changed its vision about the end of life of products and has been finding solutions, such as incorporation of wastes as alternative raw materials. Thus, the PAPERCHAIN project is focused on the valorisation of several PPI wastes into a variety of industrial and construction solutions:

- Lime mud/ash as filler in precast concrete (Circular Case 1a)
- Green Liquor dregs (GLDs) and slacker grits as filler and fine aggregate in asphalt pavement (Circular case 1b)
- Wastepaper ash (WPA) as hydraulic road binder applications in transport infrastructures or road sector (Circular case 2)
- Paper Sludge Ash (PSA) and Deinking Paper Sludge (DPS) as slope stabilization or gabions walls construction material in railway sector (Circular case 3)
- Green liquor dregs as reactive sealing layers for acid rock drainage mitigation in mineral waste deposits in mining sector (Circular case 5)

These wastes were applied here as alternative raw materials in different products, but when their end of life is reached, these products will need a recycling solution to optimize their life cycle. Thus, Circular cases 1, 2, 3 and 5 were carried out in Portugal, Spain, Slovenia and Sweden, respectively. Each recycling solution must also follow the legislation of the country where the product is made. Accordingly, one can conclude that:

- In Circular Case 1, the future CDW from CC1a) and CC1b) have a high recyclability potential due to the low amount of incorporated PPI wastes in precast concrete (case 1a) or bituminous mixture (1b). together with the fact that both have already a recycling established framework where the CC1 developed products can also comply with.

- Recycling trials for soil-stabilised layers of Circular Case 2 have shown that there are no changes in terms of soil classification according to the Spanish Road Regulations.

- Laboratory tests show that recyclability potential of the composite MUDIPEL in Circular Case 3 is high and could be used again as a back-fill material for mining pits or other geotechnical structures.

- In the circular case 5, the recycling analysis of the product developed is not performed as the function provided by the GLDs will be required at the pilot (mining site) for an unforeseeable amount of time and is therefore considered as a final storage for these materials.

- Circular case 4 is not included in this assessment, as the bioethanol produced is the same molecule as the standard ethanol. The demonstration will continue with the production of the ethyl chloride from the bioethanol but again the molecule is the same. Both chemicals are basic compounds, commodities which recyclability does not make sense as for the rest of circular cases. CC1, CC2, CC3 and CC5 are composite materials at the end of the production chain, with a final destination. On the contrary, CC4 compounds are raw materials with different origin but with no compositional differences with the usual ones. For this reason, it was decided during the Grant Agreement preparation, not to include Circular Case 4 in the recyclability analysis.

Contact:

Victor Ferreira

Dep Eng Civil, Universidade de Aveiro

3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

victorf@ua.pt

Keywords

Recycling	End of life	Recommendations	New solutions	Valorisation
Circular Economy	Recycled aggregates	Transport Infrastructure	Concrete	Mining

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Abbreviations and acronyms:

- CDW: Construction and demolition waste
- EWL: European waste list
- LM: Lime Mud
- MB – Methylene-Blue
- PPI: Pulp and Paper Industry
- WPA: Waste Paper Ash
- GLD: Green Liquor Dreg
- WPA: Waste Paper Ash
- PSA: Paper Sludge Ash
- DPS: Deinking Sludge Ash
- DOC: Dissolved organic Carbone
- TDS: Total dissolved solid
- TOC: Total Organic Carbone
- BTEX: Benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylene
- PCB: polychlorinated biphenyl
- PAH: Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

1 Introduction

Work Package 4 (WP4) is running from M6 to M24 and deals with the preparation and test of the circular models at **pre-industrial scale**. This preparation is crucial to carry out the WP5, with the execution of the planned demonstrators.

Within WP4, the anticipation of possible limitations and constraints and the solutions to overcome them, was a task already performed (T4.1, [M6-M12]). The following two tasks 4.2 and 4.3 are simultaneous [M12-M24]. Task 4.2 takes in consideration the needed requirements to implement the demonstrators ("**Meeting requirements**").

The present report corresponds to **task 4.3 - Recycling potential analysis**.

In order to close the cycle, the recyclability of the end of life stage of the products developed will be assessed in cases such as concrete including lime mud filler; asphalt with GLDs; soil cement and stabilised layers; WPA/DPS composites and GLDs on mining soil covers.

This document concerns only with **Project Deliverable 4.3** (D4.3) which involves a "*Recycling analysis of the end-of life of developed products*". Linked directly with task 4.3 (M12-M24). This report deal with the recyclability of the new solutions and recommendations for managing the end of life of the new products

2 Industrial Sectors and Wastes involved

The PAPERCHAIN project is focused on the valorisation of several PPI waste streams into a variety of industrial and constructive solutions. In Table 1 the approached waste streams, industrial sectors and applications are exposed. These circular cases 1, 2, 3 and 5 are being carried out in Portugal, Spain, Slovenia and Sweden, respectively.

Around the world, civil engineering works use normally primary raw material, for example, natural aggregate and soil. However, society discovered new forms to reduce its use or its full replacement by secondary aggregates through recycled and artificial aggregates, or aggregates from processing of wastes and sub products produced in the industrial activity.

The construction sector consumes a large amount of resources and more than half of the emissions of greenhouse gas worldwide are related to materials and resources management. Replacement of primary by secondary raw material in civil engineering works reduces considerably the environmental impact.

TABLE 1. SUMMARY OF PPI WASTE STREAMS AND APPLICATIONS.

<i>Waste stream</i>	<i>Valorization Scenario</i>	<i>Application</i>	<i>Circular Case</i>
Lime mud/ash	Construction manufacturing	Filler in pre-cast concrete	1a
Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) and Slaker Grits	Construction manufacturing	Filler and Fine aggregate in asphalt pavements.	1b
Waste Paper Ash (WPA)	Transport Infrastructures Road Sector	Hydraulic Road Binder applications	2
Paper Sludge Ash (PSA) and Deiking Paper Sludge (DPS)	Railway Sector	Slope stabilization Gabion walls construction material	3
Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs)	Mining Sector	Reactive sealing layers for acid rock drainage mitigation in mine waste deposits	5

The civil construction sector uses many materials, being the aggregates one of the materials most used by sector. Concrete uses 70% of aggregates and pavements account for up to 90% of aggregates. In addition, population continues to grow and consequently consumes more raw materials and produce more wastes. In summary, waste can't be looked as a substance that does not have any utility to human activity. Over the last years, society changed its vision about waste and researched new solutions with wastes incorporation. Solutions go from recycling to reuse.

The civil construction sector is a producer and, at the same time, a consumer. In the first case, consumes high amounts of natural resources, and, in the second case, produces a significant volume of wastes, but its origin and composition are quite variable.

Natural aggregates are a very important raw material used in transport infrastructures and its consumption results in a reduction of available aggregates in the earth's surface.

The current solution has been opening new quarries to extract its materials. However, this activity has a high environmental impact associated. On the other hand, production of recycled aggregates is an alternative solution.

The products that contains recycled aggregates must be competitive with traditional ones, namely at quality and economic level (fewer costs of production and transportation). Quality of the final product depends on the proprieties of aggregates in the origin and all phases of processing until final application.

Therefore, recycling has some advantages, as protection of the environment through a less extraction of granular materials in a stone quarry or gravel pits (extraction activities, visual impact, destruction of the ecosystems).

When applying the philosophy of the four R's to the Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW), they can have many destination/uses depending on where they are generated, usually in conservation and/or rehabilitation works. Table 2 shows some options to use CDW that are in accordance with the philosophy of the four R's.

TABLE 2. SOME OPTIONS TO USE CDW THAT ARE IN ACCORDANCE WITH PHILOSOPHY OF THE FOUR R'S.

<i>Option</i>	<i>Solution</i>
Reutilization of the CDW	Reutilization, at the construction site or outside the construction site, with its original function
Recycling of the CDW	Treatment and processing, on or off site, with the recuperation of materials of high market value. Recycling, on or off site, to a function less noble (including land movement that isn't essential).
Final destination to the CDW	Incineration, off site, with or without recuperation of energy produced. Landfill of segregation or no segregation wastes

2.1 Circular Case 1 - Construction sector: concrete and asphalt.

In Portugal and the European Union, wastes have legislation associated, as can be seen in Table 3.

TABLE 3. LEGISLATION ASSOCIATED TO WASTE IN PORTUGAL AND EUROPEAN UNION.

Country	Legislation	Summary
European Union	Directive 2008/98/EC, November 19 th	It indicates a legal framework for treating waste in the EU. Its focus passes by protection of the environment and public health. In addition, shows the importance of compatible waste management, recovery and recycling techniques to reduce pressure on resources and improve their use.
	Decision 2014/955/EU, December 18 th	It changes the decision 2000/532/CE and define new European waste list in accordance with the directive 2008/98/EC.
	Directive 2015/1127, July 10 th	It changes the annex II of the directive 2008/98/EC.
	Decree-Law n.º 178/2006, September 5 th	It passes the regime general of wastes, and applies any operations of collection, transport, storage, storing, treatment, valorization and elimination of wastes, as well as operations of land decontamination and monitoring of locals of deposition after the closure of the respectively installations.
Portugal	Decree-Law n.º 73/2011, June 17 th	It introduces the European Directive 2008/98/EC at Portuguese legislation and changes some articles of the Decree-Law n.º 178/2006.
	Decree-Law n.º 183/2009, August 10 th	It shows the legal regime of deposition of wastes in landfill and technical characteristics. Also, defines the requirements to conceive, licence, construction explore and close the landfill.
	Ordinance n.º 209/2014, March 3 rd	It defines the elements that shall join the licensing of the operations of storage , storing, treatment, valorization and elimination of wastes.
	Ordinance n.º 1023/2006, September 20 th	It defines the elements that shall join the licensing of the operations of storage , storing, treatment, valorization and elimination of wastes.

Ordinance n.º 50/2007, March 3 rd	It approves the model of licence to realization of operations of waste management.
Ordinance n.º 145/2017 , March 3 rd	It defines the rules applicable to road transport, rail, fluvial, sea and air transport of waste in national territory. And, creates the electronic waste tracking guides (e-GAR).
Decree law n.º 46/2008 , March 12 th	It establishes the regime of operations of CDW management, but was changed by decree law n.º 73/2011 June 17 th .

According to with the decision 2014/955/EU of December 18th, the European Waste List (EWL) has twenty chapters for wastes, that were gathered by specific area of activity generator of waste, as can be seen in Table 4. In the case of Construction and demolition waste (CDW) is at chapter 17, and has seven subcategories, as can be seen in Table 5.

CDW is originating from works of construction, reconstruction, ampliation, alteration, conservation and demolition and collapse of buildings. Moreover, it is considered a waste stream.

Recycled material shows a high heterogeneity, due to an enormous variety of CDW components. Each CDW sample has its percentages of materials and is never the same from work for work. Heterogeneity depends on many factors, such as type of construction and its use, geographic location, construction processes used, construction period and respective applied materials, and the moment of collecting the sample. Therefore, and in general, recycled aggregates of CDW show physical, geometry and mechanical characteristics similar showed by natural aggregates, favoring its application.

TABLE 4. CHAPTERS OF EWC.

Chapter	Designation
01	Wastes resulting from exploration, mining, quarrying, physical and chemical treatment of minerals
02	Wastes from agriculture, horticulture, aquaculture, forestry, hunting and fishing, food preparation and processing
03	Wastes from wood processing and the production of panels and furniture, pulp, paper and cardboard
04	Wastes from the leather, fur and textile industries
05	Wastes from petroleum refining, natural gas purification and pyrolytic treatment of coal

06	Wastes from inorganic chemical processes
07	Wastes from organic chemical processes
08	Wastes from the manufacture, formulation, supply and use (MFSU) of coatings (paints, varnishes and vitreous enamels), adhesives, sealants and printing inks
09	Wastes from the photographic industry
10	Wastes from thermal processes
11	Wastes from chemical surface treatment and coating of metals and other materials; non-ferrous hydrometallurgy
12	Wastes from shaping and physical and mechanical surface treatment of metals and plastics
13	Oil wastes and wastes of liquid fuels (except edible oils, 05 and 12)
14	Waste organic solvents, refrigerants and propellants (except 07 and 08)
15	Waste packaging; absorbents, wiping cloths, filter materials and protective clothing not otherwise specified
16	Wastes not otherwise specified in the list
17	Construction and demolition wastes (including excavated soil from contaminated sites)
18	Wastes from human or animal health care and/or related research (except kitchen and restaurant wastes not arising from immediate health care)
19	Wastes from waste management facilities, off-site waste water treatment plants and the preparation of water intended for human consumption and water for industrial use
20	Municipal wastes (household waste and similar commercial, industrial and institutional wastes) including separately collected fractions

TABLE 5. SUBCATEGORIES OF THE CDW

Subchapter	Categories
17 01	Concrete, bricks, tiles and ceramics
17 02	Wood, glass and plastic
17 03	bituminous mixtures, coal and tarred products
17 04	metals (including their alloys)
17 05	Soil (including excavated soil from contaminated sites), stones and dredging spoil
17 06	Insulation materials and asbestos-containing construction materials
17 07	Gypsum- based construction material
18 08	Other construction and demolition wastes

The use of CDW in construction works shall follow the national and EU technical norms. In the absence of applicable technical norms, specifications by national laboratories or approved by the government or environmental authority.

In Portugal, there are seven specifications that help to normalize usage of CDW, Table 6, that can be applied in different uses from aggregates for concrete, bituminous mixtures, kerbsides, landfills, unbound sub-base and base or bound with hydraulics binder of roads pavements, forest and rural roads, and ditches.

TABLE 6. SPECIFICATIONS ELABORATED BY LNEC (NATIONAL LABORATORY OF CIVIL ENGINEERING) FOR UTILIZATION OF CDW.

Specification	Title
E 471	Guide for the use of coarse recycled aggregate in concrete
E 472	Guide for the use the production of recycled hot mix asphalt
E 473	Guide for the use of recycled aggregates in unbound pavement layers
E 474	Guide for the use of recycled materials coming from construction and demolition waste in embankment and capping layer of transport infrastructures
E 483	Guide for the use of recycled aggregates from reclaimed asphalt for unbound road pavement layers
E 484	Guide for the use of materials resulting from construction and demolition waste in rural and forest roads
E 485	Guide for the use of materials resulting from construction and demolition waste in backfill of trenches

CDW have a group of technical and environmental requirements to comply, in order to be used as aggregates. In the case of environmental aspects, the specifications inform that CDW shall be inert or don't have tar or other pollutants, as well as asbestos. If on the contrary, the waste doesn't fit the previous condition, they shall be deposited in a landfill and its choice depends on determined leaching values in certain parameters. In Portugal, there are three types of landfill for inert, non-dangerous and dangerous waste. Table 7 shows limit values to classify wastes and choose the type of landfill that is in accordance with Decree-Law 183/2009, August 10th. Also identifies list admissible wastes in a landfill for inert waste without testing, as can be seen in Table 8.

TABLE 7. LEACHING LIMIT VALUES TO CLASSIFY WASTES AND CHOOSE TYPE OF LANDFILL.

Component	Limit		
	Inert waste	No Dangerous Waste	Dangerous Waste
As	0,5	5	25
Ba	20	100	300
Cd	0,04	2	5
Cr total	0,5	20	70
CU	2	50	100
Hg	0,01	0,5	2
Mo	0,5	10	30
Ni	0,4	10	40
Pb	0,5	10	50
Sb	0,06	0,7	5
Se	0,1	0,5	7
Zn	4	50	200
Chloride	800	50000	25000
Fluoride	10	250	500

Sulphate	1000	20000	50000
Phenol index	1	-	-
DOC	500	1000	1000
TDS	4000	60000	100000

TABLE 8. LIST ADMISSIBLE WASTES IN LANDFILL TO INERT WASTE WITHOUT TESTING.

<i>EWC code</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Restriction</i>
10 11 03	Waste glass-based fibrous materials	Just without organic agglutinant
15 01 07	Glass packaging	Just selected CDW: i) with low contents of other types of materials (like metals, plastic, soil, organics, wood, rubber, etc); II) the origin of the waste must be known; III) No CDW from constructions polluted with inorganic or organic dangerous substances, e.g. because of production processes in the construction, soil pollution, storage and usage of pesticides or other dangerous substances, etc., unless it is made clear that the demolished construction was not significantly polluted; IV) No CDW from constructions, treated, covered or painted with materials, containing dangerous substances in significant amounts.
17 01 01	Concrete	
17 01 02	Bricks	
17 01 03	Tiles and ceramics	
17 01 07	mixtures of concrete, bricks, tiles and ceramics materials	
17 02 02	Glass	-
17 05 04	Soil and stones	Excluding superficial soil and tur; Excluding Soil and stones of contaminated local
19 12 05	Glass	-
20 01 02	Glass	Just glass collected separately
20 02 02	Soil and stones	Just of wastes of gardens and parks; Excluding superficial soil and turf

In the technical part, each specification classifies waste in different classes (Table 10) and these depend on waste composition (Table 9). The composition is determined in accordance with standard EN 933-11:2009 "Tests for geometrical properties of aggregates. Part 11: Classification test for the constituents of coarse recycled aggregate." After that, new aggregates are characterized by a group of testing and are classified with a category. Also, each specification presents a group of application rules.

TABLE 9. CONSTITUENTS OF COARSE RECYCLED AGGREGATES.

<i>Constituent</i>	<i>Description</i>
Rc	Concrete, concrete products, mortar, concrete masonry units
Ru	Unbound aggregate, natural stone, hydraulically bound aggregate
Rb	Clay masonry units (i.e. bricks and tiles), calcium silicate masonry units, aerated non- floating concrete
Ra	Bituminous materials
Rg	Glass

X	Other: cohesive (i.e. clay and soil), miscellaneous: metals (ferrous and non-ferrous), non-floating wood, plastic and rubber, gypsum plaster
Fl	Fluctuant material

TABLE 10. COMPOSITION OF RECYCLED AGGREGATES.

Specification	Class	R _c (%)	R _c +R _u (%)	R _b (%)	R _a (%)	R _g (%)	R _c + R _u +R _g (%)	R _b + R _s (%)	X+ R _g (%)	X (%)	Fl (cm ³ /kg)
E 471	ARB1	≥ 90		≤ 10	≤ 5	-	-	-	≤ 0,5	-	≤ 2
	ARB2	≥ 70		≤ 30	≤ 5	-	-	-	≤ 1	-	≤ 2
	ARC	≥ 90			≤ 10	-	-	-	≤ 2	-	≤ 2
E 473	B	-		≤ 5	≤ 5	≤ 5	≥ 90	-	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
	C	-		≤ 30	≤ 30	≤ 5	≥ 50	-	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
E 474	B	-		-	≤ 5	≤ 10	≥ 90	≤ 10	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
	MB	-		-	≥ 30	≤ 25	≤ 70	≤ 70	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
	C	-		-	≤ 30	≤ 25	without limit	Without limit	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
E 483	RAP	-		-	> 30 and ≤ 100	≤ 5	≤ 40	-	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
E 484	CRA	-		-	without limit	≤ 25	without limit	without limit	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
	CRB	-		-	≤ 80	≤ 5	≥ 20	≤ 10	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
	CRC	-		-	≤ 30	≤ 5	≥ 50	≤ 10	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
E 485	MR1	-		-	≤ 30	≤ 25	≥ 70	≤ 30	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
	MR2	-		-	without limit	≤ 25	without limit	Without limit	-	≤ 1	≤ 5
	MR3	-		-	≤ 10	≤ 5	without limit	Without limit	-	≤ 1	≤ 5

2.1.1 Recycling potential analyses in concrete

Specification E 471 provides recommendations and establishes minimum requirements for the use of coarse recycled aggregates covered by standard NP EN 12620 on production of hydraulic binders concrete. It does not set demands and rules for fine aggregates recycled aggregates.

CDW processing has normally 4 operations: screening, primary reduction, crushing and sieving. The storage shall be made according to origin and main components. Also, there is the possibility to combine different wastes. However, the mix shall be made in controlled conditions, in order to ensure the uniformity of recycled material.

In environmental terms, recycled aggregates must not have strange elements that harm the environment and the concrete performance. The leaching test for wastes gave a result of inert waste, according to classification of wastes for inert landfill.

In relation to alkali-silica reaction (ASR), the Civil Engineering National Laboratory (LNEC) advises on how to evaluate this property. The specification LNEC E 461 indicates test procedures for this property and the value shall be declared.

TABLE 11. PROPRIETIES AND MINIMUM REQUIREMENTS FOR RECYCLED AGGREGATES TO ALL APPLICATIONS.

Properties	Test standard	ARB1	ARB2	ARC
Size	EN 933-1	Satisfy section 4,2 of		
Grading	EN 933-1	Satisfy section 4,3,2		
Constituents	EN 933-11	Comply a class of the Table 10		
Sharpe	EN 933-3	FL ₃₅	Fl ₅₀	Category to declare
Fines content	EN 933-1	f ₄	f ₄	f ₃
Resistance to fragmentation	EN 1097-2	LA ₅₀	Category declare	-
Particle size	EN 1097-6	≥2200 kg/m ³	≥2200 kg/m ³	≥2000 kg/m ³
Water absorption	EN 1097-6	≤ 7%	≤ 7%	Category declare
Alkali-silica reaction	See LNEC E 461	Category declare		
Volume stability	EN 1367-4 (annex A)	Retraction ≤ 0,075%		
Content soluble chlorides in acid	EN 1744-5	Value declare		
Content acid soluble sulphate in water	EN 1744-1	SS _{0,2}		
Content acid soluble sulphate in acid	EN 1744-1, section 12	AS _{0,8}		
Content total sulphur	EN 1744-1, section 11	S ≤ 1,0%		
Organic constituents which alter the rate of setting and hardening of concrete	EN 1744-1, section 15	Satisfy subheadings a) and b) of section 6,4,1		
Soluble constituents in water which alter the rate of setting and hardening of concrete	EN 1744-6	Value declare (section 6,4,1)		
Release of dangerous substances	EN 12457-4	Wastes for deposition in landfill to inert waste		

ARB1 and ARB2 classes are constituted mainly by concrete, mixed or not with unbound aggregates. ARC class (composited recycled aggregates) has as main components: concrete, unbound aggregates, and brick elements. The last class does not have a percentage associated to each material.

The specification shows two tables with requirements for recycled aggregates. Table 11 presents proprieties and minimum requirements for recycled aggregates to all applications. Table 12 indicates proprieties and minimum requirements for recycled aggregates for certain uses.

TABLE 12. PROPRIETIES AND MINIMUM REQUIREMENTS FOR RECYCLED AGGREGATES FOR CERTAIN USAGE.

Properties	Test standard	ARB1	ARB2	ARC	Application
Alkali content	NP 1382	Value determinate			Concrete with reactive aggregates
Lightweight contaminators	NP EN 1444-1, section 14,2	Satisfy section G4 of annex of EN 12620			Surface finish concrete

Application of recycled aggregates in concrete depends on conditions on the previous tables. Also, there is the possibility to use aggregates that do not comply with the previous properties. In this case, there must be a study to analyse the influence of the properties on the performance of concrete. In elements that are in contact with water for human consumption, concrete with recycled aggregates can't be used.

The amount of recycled aggregates depends on the type of concrete to produce. In the case of reinforced concrete, aggregate rate is between 20% and 25% for aggregates of ARB1 and ARB2 class, respectively. On top of that, there is an upper limit for resistance class and environment exposition class (Table 13). Regularization or filling and simple concrete in not aggressive environment do not have any limit of incorporation for class ARB1 and ARB2 aggregates.

TABLE 13. APPLICATIONS CONDITIONS.

Recycled aggregate class	Resistance class	Incorporation Percentage	Environment exposition class
ARB1	C _{40/50}	25%	X0, XC1, XC2, XC3, XC4, XS1, XA1
ARB2	C _{35/45}	20%	

ARC class must be applied only in concrete of filling or regularization without any structural function and in non-aggressive environments. Other elements can have this concrete too; however, there must be studies before application.

2.1.2 Recycling potential analyses in bituminous mixtures

The guidebook of *Infraestruturas de Portugal* (national regulations) considers three different methodologies of recycled mix. One methodology is “in situ” and the production temperature is cold. The two other solutions are produced in a processing central. The only difference is the production temperature (hot or semi-warm).

In the case of production of recycled hot mix asphalt, incorporation rate of reclaimed asphalt is dependent on the type of plant. In a continuous plant, incorporation can be between 10 and 50%. While in a discontinuous plant, incorporation can be between 10 and 30%. Or up to 70%, if it is installed on another dryer drum.

There are two groups of strange material (Group 1 and 2). The group 1 can contain concrete (including concrete products), bricks, sub-base material (excluding natural aggregate) and metal. The group 2 can own synthetic material, wood and plastic. After this each group is classified in categories, as can be seen in Table 14.

TABLE 14. CATEGORIES OF STRANGE MATERIAL.

Categories	Group 1	Group 2
F1	≤ 1	≤ 0,1
F5	≤ 5	≤ 0,1
Fdec	Content and type of strange material to be declared	

Also, the recuperated binder has to be characterized, namely, penetration (P) and delta ring and ball (S). The S15 category is calculated for average value of samples and it must be 15 or more. The S70 category is also obtained for average value of samples and it must be 70 or less. When the value doesn't comply with the limit, it can be designated as Pdec or Sdec.

Maximum content of water and aggregates size in reclaimed bituminous mixture must be 5% and 32 mm. Particle and maximum size and percentage medium of binder in reclaimed bituminous mixture do not have any limit.

Results of the former properties are joined in three categories (MBR1, MBR2 and MBR3). Table 15 shows grouped values, maximum rate of incorporation and utilization domain (kind layer).

TABLE 15. MAXIMUM RATES OF WASTES INCORPORATION IN BITUMINOUS MIXTURES

Categories	MBR1		MBR2	MBR3
Strange material	F1	F5	F5	F5
Kind binder	Bitumen of paving	Bitumen of paving	Bitumen of paving	Modified or hard bitumen of paving

Characteristics of Reclaimed binder	P ₁₅ or P ₇₀	P ₁₅ or P ₇₀	P _{dec} or S _{dec}	P _{dec} or S _{dec}
Utilization domain	Wearing layer	Wearing or regularization or base layer	Wearing or regularization or base layer	Ligation or regularization or base layer
Maximum rate of incorporation	10%	50%	25%	10%

The values for the rate of incorporation depend on the results of the formulation study, characteristics of reclaimed binder and manufacturing process. Also, it is possible to use higher incorporation rates, provided, evaluate reclaimed binder characteristics on final mixture and performance of the mixture.

According to national regulations, the final product of recycled mixture must have at the same properties of traditional mixture.

In the case of production of semi-warm recycled mixture in plant, the maximum recycling rate is 100%. The recycled material must be framed in category F1 and P15 for strange material and recuperated binder, respectively. In addition, Table 16 shows the limits of particle size distribution of this material.

TABLE 16. LIMITS OF PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION.

Sieve size (mm)	Percentage passing material	
	Fuse I	Fuse II
-	100	-
40	90 to 100	100
32	69 to 95	80 to 100
20	52 to 82	62 to 89
12,5	40 to 70	49 to 77
8	25 to 53	31 to 58
4	15 to 40	19 to 42
2	2 to 20	2 to 20
0,5	0 to 10	0 to 10
0,25	0 to 3	0 to 3

This technology uses a slow-breaking cationic bituminous emulsion. But before that, the recovered binder shall be characterised in terms of solubility, asphaltenes content and delta ring and ball. The final product should be according to Table 16. The maximum size (first sieve that contains more 10% by mass) will be less 1/3 of the thickness of the recycled layer. Table 17 shows minimum values for recycled bituminous mixture.

TABLE 17. LIMITS FOR SEMI WARM RECYCLED BITUMINOUS RECYCLING.

Characteristics	Values
-----------------	--------

Resistance to compression in dry (MPa)	> 3
Resistance to compression after immersion (MPa)	>2,5
Conserved strength (%)	> 75
Voids (%)	4 to 10

Recycled mixture in situ can use cement or bituminous emulsion like binder. In case of cement use, recycled material cannot have organic matter and other products that can affect setting time of cement. In addition, it must not show potential reactivity of alkalis with cement. Table 18 shows other properties that recycled aggregates must comply to use cement as binder.

TABLE 18. PROPERTIES/REQUIREMENTS OF RECYCLED MATERIAL.

Properties	Values
Liquidity limit	< 35
Plasticity index	≤15
Maximum size (mm)	< 80
Percentage of passing material on size 4 mm (%)	> 30

Final Product must have a percentage of binder and a compressive strength (7 days) higher than 3% and 2,5 MPa, respectively. Recycled aggregates for in situ mixture with bituminous emulsion must comply with the particle size distribution of Table 16. Some final characteristics of recycled mixture should be according to Table 19.

TABLE 19. SOME MINIMUM REQUIREMENTS FOR RECYCLED MIXTURE WITH EMULSION.

Properties	Values
Granulometric	To frame in fuse I or II
Percentage of residual bitumen (%)	< 1,5%
Compressive resistance (dry) (MPa)	>2 or 3
Compressive resistance after immersion (MPa)	> 2 or > 2,5
Conserved strength (%)	> 70 or 75

LNEC shows six specifications related to the use of recycled aggregates in pavements. Four LNEC Specifications (E 474, E483, E 484 and E485) have at least a category that does not have an upper limit for bituminous mixture waste. However, the specification E 473 shows a category that has an upper limit for bituminous mixture waste (30%) and lower limit (50%) for concrete, concrete products and mortars.

There is also a group of properties (physical and geometrical) that are evaluated. This characterization attributes a category. Table 20 presents the categories for each specification.

TABLE 20. EXISTENT CATEGORIES IN THE SPECIFICATIONS.

Specification	Categories			
E 473	AGER 1	AGER 2	AGER 3	-
E474	MAT1	MAT2	-	-
E 473	-	-	-	-
E484	CR1	CR2	CR3	CR4
E 485	CE/LA	PSA2/PIA	PSA1	-

Complying with minimum requirements of the specifications, these can be applied in certain applications. Table 21 and 22 shows the minimum requirements for bituminous mixtures wastes and indicates category and associated specification.

TABLE 21. MINIMUM REQUIREMENTS FOR BITUMINOUS MIXTURE WASTE (SPECIFICATION E 473 AND E 483).

Specification	E473		E483
	AGER1	AGER2	
Category			
Class	B	B	RAP
Size	0/31,5	0/31,5	0/31,5
Oversize	OC ₇₅	OC ₈₀	OC ₇₅
Grain size Class	-	-	G _p
Fines content	UF ₉ LF ₂	UF ₉ LF ₂	UF ₉
Fines quality	MB _{0/D} ≤ 1	MB _{0/D} ≤ 0,8	MB _{0/D} ≤ 0,8
Percentage of crushed and broken surfaces	C _{50/30}	C _{50/10}	C _{90/3}
Resistance to fragmentation (LA) and wear (MDE)	LA ₄₅ and MDE ₄₅ or LA+MDE ≤ 85	LA ₄₀ and MDE ₄₀ or LA+MDE ≤ 75	LA ₄₀
Content acid soluble sulphate in water	SS _{0,7}	SS _{0,7}	SS _{0,7}
Realised of dangerous substances	Inert Waste		
Binder content	-	-	≤ 8%

TABLE 22. MINIMUM REQUIREMENTS FOR BITUMINOUS MIXTURE WASTE (SPECIFICATION E 474, E 484 AND E 485).

Specification	E474		E484		E485
Category	MAT1	MAT2	CR1	CR2	PSA2/PIA
Class	MB	MB	CRA	CRA	MR2

Maximum Size (mm)	$D_{max} \leq 150$	$D_{max} \leq 80$	$D_{max} \leq 180$	$D_{max} \leq 80$	$D_{max} \leq 180$
Fines content	$\leq 10\%$ (on sieve 80 μm)		-	$\leq 12\%$ (on sieve 63 μm)	-
Fines quality	$MB_{0/D} \leq 2$	$MB_{0/D} \leq 1$	-	$MB_{0/D} \leq 2$	-
Resistance to fragmentation (LA) and wear (MDE)	-	-	-	$LA \leq 50$	-
Content acid soluble sulphate in water	0,7%	0,7%	$\leq 0,7\%$	$\leq 0,7\%$	$\leq 0,7\%$
Realised of dangerous substances	Inert Waste				

All wastes must be classified as inert wastes, according to decree law 183/2009. In the case of the use of bituminous mixtures wastes, these cannot contain tar. If recycled aggregates do not comply with the minimum requirements, they can be mixed with natural aggregates, in order to satisfy the requirements.

According to E473 specification, the uses of recycled aggregates (C class and category AGER1) are not recommended in base unbound layers of pavements. In sub-base unbound layers limits up to 50 of average daily traffic of heavy vehicles by road. But if recycled aggregate has AGER2 category and C class, the number of traffic goes up to 150 in both layers.

Regarding E474 specification, the MB class and MAT1 or MAT2 category can only be applied in embankment of transport infrastructures.

RAP class of the E 483 specification can be applied in unbound sub-base and base layers until 150 of average daily traffic of heavy vehicles by road. When the composition has at least 80 % of bituminous mixture waste, these should be mixed with other recycled or nature aggregates and percentage should be up to 20%. Before this application should analyse E 472 in the first place, in order to verify its requirements.

The E484 has a class (CRA) that does not have limit for bituminous mixture waste. This class can be framed in CR1 or CR2 category. The materials that have CR2 can be applied in embankment for rural and forest roads, and sub-base or bed pavement. If materials have CR1 category can only be applied in embankment for rural and forest roads.

The MR2 class that does not have a limit for bituminous mixture waste. If wastes comply PSA2/PIA category of the E485, can be applied in backfill of trenches under pavements of transport infrastructures, strolls and green spaces.

2.2 Circular Case 2 - Transport infrastructure: Roads

This Circular Case uses Wastepaper Paper Ash (WPA) based alternative Hydraulic Road Binder (HRB) for the replacement of cement and/or quicklime in soil stabilization works in road projects. This Circular Case comprises three demonstrations:

- a) HRB in two different types of subgrade applications in roads by means of in-situ stabilized soil layers. The demonstrations (already performed) can be divided into two different categories of roads:
 - 1 Km length country road for **S-EST2** demonstration, in the municipality of Ejea de los Caballeros (Aragon, Spain). The soil stabilization was carried out using a **3% of WPFA by mass** of dry soil as Hydraulic Road Binder.
 - 1 Km length of an **S-EST3** stabilized layer according to the Spanish Road Regulation. This road is localised in the municipality of Villamayor de Gállego (Aragon, Spain). Soil stabilisation was carried out using a **5% of WPFA by mass** of soil on dry weight basis.
- b) WPFA valorized as soil-cement, produced at plant in subbase applications will be demonstrated in a stretch of 250 m of length within an internal service road in a test track complex in Toledo (Spain).

The demonstrations S-EST2 & S-EST3 were held in Aragon region (Spain). SAICA was the WPFA provider, and ACCIONA CONSTRUCTION SA the waste manager and end user – road constructor. UPC provided technical assistance. All works were held in public domains in Aragon.

The Spanish Road Regulation “PG3” governs the utilization of Hydraulic Road Binders for road construction in soil stabilisation of subgrade and subbase layers in Spain. Although it does not foresee any other HRB apart from cement or quick lime, some relevant UE harmonized specifications have been taken as reference for Circular Case 2:

TABLE 23. APPLYING SPECIFICATIONS FOR HYDRAULIC BINDERS: ROAD CONSTRUCTION IN SPAIN.

Specification	Details
EN 13282-2:2015. (UNE-EN 13282-2:2016 Spanish version: Hydraulic road binders)	Composition, specifications and conformity criteria.
EN 197-1:2011. Cement	Part 1: Composition, specifications and conformity criteria for common cements.

EN 459-1:2015. Building lime	Part 1: Definitions, specifications and conformity criteria.
EN 196-1 : 2005. Methods of testing cement	Part 1: Determination of strength.
EN 196-2: 2013 Method of testing cement	Part 2: Chemical analysis of cement
EN 196-3: 2016. Methods of testing cement	Part 3: Determination of setting times and soundness.
EN 196-6: 2010. Methods of testing cement	Part 6: Determination of fineness.

Among all of these regulations, the reference specification for the use of Waste Paper Fly Ash (WPA) as hydraulic road binder in Circular Case 2 is the European Standard **UNE-EN13282-2 “Hydraulic road binders”**.

Its aim is to specify the conditions and requirements set for the procedure and conformity of hydraulic road binders to be employed along the treatment of base and subbase layers, level formation of the subgrade as well as in earthworks of roads, railways, airports and other type of infrastructures.

According to this rule, WPA is considered a normal hardening hydraulic road binder (nHRB). This standard allows the utilization of paper sludge ash (WPA) as a principal component of a Hydraulic Road Binder (HRB) provided they meet the following characteristics:

- Total CaO \geq 35% by mass
- (SiO₂ + Al₂O₃ + Fe₂O₃) \geq 15% by mass
- MgO \geq 5% by mass
- Free CaO \geq 7% by mass, in accordance with Standard EN 451-1
- SO₃ \leq 2% by mass
- The loss on ignition of paper sludge ash, determined in accordance with EN 196-2, but with an ignition time of one hour, or the non-calcined carbon content determined in accordance with Standard ISO 10694, should not exceed 9.0% by mass.
- If free lime (CaO), content of a normal hardening HRB, which includes quicklime as principal components, is higher than 10% by mass, the HRB must be slaked

previously to perform tests of compressive strength, setting times and volumetric stability.

In addition, HRB and HRB mortars (WPFA mixed with soil) must fulfill other requirements. Some of the most representatives will be detailed below:

HRB Compositional/Chemical requirements

- Sulphate content, expressed as the percentage of SO₃ by mass, and determined in accordance with EN 196-2, shall not exceed 4.0 % by mass as characteristic value.
- The constituents of a normal hardening hydraulic road binder, and their average proportion in the finished product, shall be recorded. The main constituents shall be declared by the manufacturer, as well as the presence of calcium if the sulphate (SO₃) content of the nHRB exceeds 4.0 % by mass.
- The composition shall meet, for all main constituents taken individually, the values documented by the manufacturer and declared within absolute tolerances ($\pm 10\%$ by mass in this case).
- The Standard mention that the proportion of paper sludge ash (WPA) as defined shall not exceed 40 % by mass (50% within the tolerance), but this requirement is resulted from existing experience at the time of publication of this European Standard. So that, we should demonstrate de viability to increase that percentage.

HRB mortars mechanical requirements

- Compressive strength of HRB must be determined in accordance with Standard EN 196-1, replacing the cement with the HRB. During this test, slaked nHRB mortars may appear dry or very dry but regardless of this aspect the specimens must be manufactured as specified in that standard.

HRB mortars physical requirements

- The fineness of a hydraulic binder for normal hardening roads must be determined by sieving in accordance with Standard EN 196-6.
- Initial setting time must be determined in accordance with EN 196-3
- Expansion must be determined in accordance with EN 196-3.

Durability requirements:

- In many applications, particularly in severe environmental conditions, the choice of binder has an influence on the durability of the finished works, e.g. soundness, frost resistance or chemical resistance. The choice of binder, particularly as regard type and strength class for different applications and

exposures, shall follow the appropriate standards and/or regulations valid in the place of use.

Regarding to the Road construction regulatory framework in Spain, the Spanish Ministry of Public Works developed and published the “**General Technical Specifications for Roadworks and Bridges (PG-3)**” (PG-3, 2014), the key document for the road construction sector. This rule constitutes a set of instructions for the development of road and bridge works; and it contains the standardized technical conditions referring to the materials and the work units.

Subsequently, all the requirements applying to soils along the road constructions are specified, including a classification of types of soils related to the intrinsic characteristics of the materials according to their chemical and mechanical characteristics and performance.

These categories, in descendent order of quality and technical performance, are Graded aggregates, Adequate, “Tolerable”, “Marginal” and Unsuitable. In addition, PG-3 rule also describes the zones of roads in which every kind of soil can be located during the road construction works, and the conditions to make it.

This classification is detailed in Table 24.

TABLE 24. SOILS CLASSIFICATION ACCORDING TO PG-3.

	Graded aggregate	“Adequate”	“Tolerable”	“Marginal”	Unsuitable
Organic Matter	<0,2% (UNE 103204)	<1% (UNE 103204)	<2% (UNE 103204)	<5% (UNE 103204)	No compliance
Soluble Salts	<0,2% (NLT 114, gypsum included)	<0,2% (NLT 114, gypsum included)	< 1% (NLT 114)	Not mentioned	No compliance
Gypsum	X	X	< 5% (NLT 115)	Not mentioned	No compliance
Grain Size	# 20 UNE > 70% # 2 UNE < 80% # 0.40 UNE < 80% # 0.080 UNE < 25%	# 20 UNE > 70% Dmax ≤ 100 mm # 2 UNE < 80% # 0.080 UNE < 35%	# 20 UNE > 70% # 0.080 UNE ≥ 35%	Not mentioned	No compliance
Liquid Limit	< 30 (UNE 103103)	< 40 (UNE 103103)	Inferior < 65 (UNE 103103);	Not mentioned	No compliance
Plasticity Index	<10 (UNE 103103, 103104)	When (LL <30), PI > 4	When LL>40, PI >0,73 (LL-	When LL>90, PI	No compliance

		(UNE 103103, UNE 103104)	20)	<0,73 (LL- 20)	
Collapse	X	X	<1% (NLT 254)	X	No compliance
Free Swelling Index	X	X	<3% (UNE 103601)	<5% (UNE 103601)	No compliance

2.2.1 Recycling potential of WPFA-modified layers

After the summary of the standardization framework controlling the utilization of Hydraulic Road Binders (**UNE-EN13282-2**) and the General Technical Specifications for Roadworks Prescriptions for Road Construction in Spain (**PG-3**) Considering all the mentioned above, it can be summarized that:

- This new raw material used as HRB (Waste Paper Fly Ash), can be assessed through the specifications affecting the product itself and by means of the compressive strength resistance of prismatic specimens of mortars manufactured with WPFA instead of cement, both according to the requirements foreseen in the aforementioned rule UNE-EN13282-2.
- The stabilized soil layers produced with WPFA as HRB and for their placement along the road constructions need to accomplish all the requirements set up according to PG-3 soil quality specifications. Thus, it can be stated that the assessment of the post-stabilization soil characteristics of the three Demos (S-EST-2, S-EST-3, Soil-Cement) and its classification can be used to compare how this process affects the characteristic parameters of the soil to be classified, by its comparison with the original values.

This information can provide a satisfying indicator about the recycling potential of the WPFA technology applied as HRB. This comparative assessment is gathered below in Table 25 and Table 26:

TABLE 25. Soils classification evolution (pg-3). S-est2 (ejea).

PG3	Natural soil	Soil after WPFA stabilisation	Stabilised soil after 180 days
Organic Matter	0,13 %	-	0.69
Soluble Salts	0.07 %	0.01	0.22
Sulfate	0.10 %	-	0.13
Gypsum	0.32 %	-	1.13

Grain Size	#20: 100% #2: 98.84 % #0.40: 96.88 % #0.08: 74.42 %		-		#20: 92.92% #2: 70.30 % #0.40: 55.50 % #0.08: 29.05 %	
Liquid Limit	26		21.2		26.0	
Plasticity Index	13.0		7.4		8.0	
Standard proctor tests	MDD	OMC	MDD	OMC	MDD	OMC
	1.90 t/m ³	12.60 %	1.85 t/m ³	13.4 %	1.95	11.0 %
Modified Proctor test	MDD	OMC	MDD	OMC	MDD	OMC
	2.05 t/m ³	9.2 %	2.03 t/m ³	10.8 %	2.02 t/m ³	10.8 %
CBR	5.6		47		48	
Collapse	0.48 %		0.16 %		0.00 %	
Free Swelling Index	2.94%		0.12 %		0.77 %	
Soil class (PG-3)	Clayey silt. "Tolerable"				Sandy clays "Tolerable"	

TABLE 26. SOILS CLASSIFICATION EVOLUTION (PG-3). S-EST3 (VILLAMAYOR).

-	Natural soil		Soil after WPFA stabilisation		Stabilised soil after 180 days	
Organic Matter	0.31 %				0.62	
Soluble Salts	0.15				0.05	
Sulfate	0.06 %		0.01 %		0.07	
Gypsum	0.04				0.30	
Grain Size	#20: 81.9% #2: 35.9 % #0.40: 22.9 % #0.08: 8.6 %				#20: 83.8% #2: 37.8 % #0.40: 22.5 % #0.08: 6.9 %	
Liquid Limit	NP		NP		NP	
Plasticity Index	NP		NP		NP	
Standard proctor tests	MDD	OMC	MDD	OMC	MDD	OMC
					2.00 t/m ³	10.4 %
Modified Proctor test	MDD	OMC	MDD	OMC	MDD	OMC
	2.16 t/m ³	7.2 %	1.98 t/m ³	8.2 %	2.05 t/m ³	8.4 %
CBR (98 %)	57		-		-	
Collapse	-		-		-	
Free Swelling Index	-		-		-	
Soil class (PG-3)	Graded aggregate		Graded aggregate		Graded aggregate	

It can be concluded that the addition of WPFA does not change the classification of the soils according to the Spanish Roads Regulation (PG3). The soil from Ejea, a Clayey silt ("tolerable") does not change. Its physical and mechanical parameters does not evolve significantly, the MDD remains more or less constant (slightly lower) and the OMC increases a bit (around 10 %), but the soluble salts does not vary, considering the natural dispersion and the low dosage of WPFA (3%). The bearing capacity is not affected and no significant variation can be interpreted.

The graded aggregate used as borrow material in Villamayor does not suffer variation in its classification. The grading curve is the same and the soluble salts do not increase significantly although the dosage here is quite higher (5 %).

The most significant changes occur in the compaction behaviour. The trend is the same as when using other standard HRBs. The MDD decreases significantly (from 2.16 to 1.98 t/m³) after the stabilisation. 6 months later, after excavating the soil, the MDD does not recover its original MDD, keeping intermediate values (2.05 t/m³). OMC increases after the stabilisation and kept similar six months later. This behaviour suggests that the excavated material would be classified in the same way as initially, although in case of

re-stabilisation, a higher dosage would be needed to achieve the same compressive strength resistance, due to the lower MDD expected for the excavated recycled material.

In addition, the evolution of the leachate was assessed prior and after the addition of WPFA to check until how extent the addition of WPA may imply an increase in the mobility of certain elements of concern. This fact has a direct effect in the soil classification according to the Royal Decree 1481/2001 of 27th of December where it is regulated the landfilling. Wastes are classified into Inert, Non-hazardous and Hazardous depending on the leaching behaviour. Despite the fact that the soil is not considered neither contaminated material nor waste, this criterion can be used as a reference to compare the leaching behaviour evolution before and after the WPFA addition and whether this could represent a certain risk in the future in the event this material could have to be excavated and disposed of. Table 27 shows the gathered data.

The leaching tests have shown that there are no changes in terms of classification from the landfilling criteria. The original soils would be considered as Non-hazardous waste and after adding WPFA the material remains under the same classification. Just the soluble salts content and the chlorides suffered a certain increase in the stabilized soil. Antimony suffered a relative increase, although it cannot be associated to WPFA, which leachability is lower than in soil.

TABLE 27. EVOLUTION OF LEACHING BEFORE AND AFTER WPFA ADDITION AND COMPARISON AGAINST THRESHOLD VALUES FOR LANDFILLING.

Parameter	Inert	Non-hazardous	Hazardous	WPFA	EJEA SOIL+3 % WPFA	VILLAMAYOR (SOIL)	VILLAMAYOR SOIL + 5 % WPFA
As	0,5	2	25	<0.05	0.019	<0,01	<0.01
Ba	20	100	300	98	0.76	0.34	1.4
Cd	0,04	1	5	<0.004	<0.01	<0,01	<0.01
Cr (Tot.)	0,5	10	70	0.13	0.24	<0,2	0.31
Cu	2	50	100	0.26	0.58	<0,2	0.37
Hg	0,01	0,2	2	<0.0005	<0.01	<0,01	<0.01
Mo	0,5	10	30	0.18	<0.2	<0,2	<0.2
Ni	0,4	10	40	<0.1	<0.2	<0,2	<0.2
Pb	0,5	10	50	0.4	<0.2	<0,05	<0.2
Sb	0,06	0,7	5	0.041	0.23	<0,01	0.19
Se	0,1	0,5	7	<0.039	<0.05	<0,05	<0.05
Zn	4	50	200	0.21	1.75	<0,2	<0.2
Chlorides	800	15000	25000	12,000	1,576.67	<50	761
Fluorides	10	150	500	6.2	15.2	<5	<5
Sulfate	1000	20000	50000	62.2	231.67	3665	266
Phenol index	1	—	—	<0.1	<0.5	<0,5	<0.5
DOC Dissolved Organic Carbon	500	800	1000	<5	68.27	58.75	36
STD Total Dissolved Solids	4000	60000	100000	36,100	6,066.67	6,260	9,660
pH	—	At least 6.0	—	12.7	11.33	11.05	11.8

Values in mg/l. Leaching tests according to a liquid / solid ratio of 10.

2.3 Circular Case 3 - Transport infrastructure: railways

For Slovenian demo case the recycled material with the commercial name MUDIPEL, will be used as the back-fill material between gabions and rock/soil slope. In Slovenia and in the European Union, waste has legislation associated, as can be seen in TABLE 28.

TABLE 28. LEGISLATION ASSOCIATED TO WASTE AND BUILDING PRODUCTS IN SLOVENIA AND THE EUROPEAN UNION.

Country	Legislation	Summary
European Union	Directive 2008/98/EC, of 19 November, 2008 th	It indicates a legal framework for treating waste in the EU. Its focus passes by protection of the environment and public health. In addition, shows the importance of compatible waste management, recovery and recycling techniques to reduce pressure on resources and improve their use.
	DIRECTIVE (EU) 2018/851 of 30 May 2018	This document is amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste.
	Decision 2014/955/EU, December 18 th	It changes the decision 2000/532/CE and define new European waste list in accordance with the directive 2008/98/EC.
Slovenia	Decree-Law n.° UL RS št.93/2013	In the article 9 of that directive using other (recycled) material for railway construction stabilisation and soil/rock slope stabilisation near the railway line is possible. The same directive in the article 4 allows using of Technical Specification for Roads (TSC), where it is reasonably appropriate.
	Decree-Law n.° UL RS, No. 61/11	Eluates must comply with the requirements of the Decree on the Landfill of Waste at Landfills (UL RS, No. 61/11) – “inert waste
	Decree-Law n.° Construction Products Act - ZGPro-1	The Slovenian Law on the Construction Products.
	Ordinance n.° No. 3210-9 / 2002-23 of 20 December 2006	In accordance with Article 22 of ZGPro-1 (the Slovenian Law on the Construction Products), ZAG continues to be nominated as the Slovenian Technical Approval Authority

According to the provisions of Article 5 of the Construction Products Act - ZGPro-1, the manufacturer may demonstrate the essential characteristics of the construction product on the basis of the Slovenian Technical Approval (STS) before placing it on the market, if that product is not covered by the harmonized technical specification. Issuing of the Declaration of Conformity is also mandatory for the producer.

Slovenian Technical Approval is a national technical specification, which comes into force when harmonized technical specifications (harmonized standard or European technical approval) are not available. Certification may not therefore be based on the EU standard, but the principles of certifying construction products and/or production are.

According to the legislation in Slovenia, a recycled material, which is not covered by the harmonized standard, should not be used for the building and infrastructure without an STS. For every recycled material an STS has to be granted based on the relevant laboratory and field investigations. For recycled materials, appropriate chemical and mechanical tests have to be performed to prove compliance with mechanical and environmental requirements.

In Slovenia, there are several technical specifications that help to encourage the use of recycled materials. The most common applications of back-fill materials are presented in TABLE 29.

TABLE 29. SLOVENIAN TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS FOR BACK-FILL MATERIAL

Specification	Title
TSC 05.800:2001	For traffic infrastructure the Slovenian Technical Specification for roads (TSC), are used which includes also technical requirements for the use of recycling material in the road construction
TSC 05.413	Requirements for back-fill material near the structure and infrastructure.
TSC 06.740:2003	The properties of the recycled materials have to be proven with the demo field and for this procedure the technical specification exists.

The technical characteristics of the back-fill material are determined in Technical specification TSC 05.413 - Construction of embankments, fillers and clay charges. Technical specifications also allow the use of fly ash as a filler material. For paper fly ash as filler material in the structure, the most important (critical) characteristics are:

- Optimal water content
- Optimal density (TABLE 30)
- Modulus below the construction (TABLE 31)
- Environmental acceptability

TABLE 30. OPTIMAL DENSITY REQUIREMENTS FOR BACK-FILL MATERIAL

Material/thickness of the layer	Required compression
Material up to 2 m of thickness	95 SPP*
Material up more than 2 m of thickness	92 SPP*
Material/thickness of the layer	Required compression

TABLE 31. IN-SITU TESTS FOR CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL

Material	Required modulus below the road construction		
	E_{v2}	E_{v2}/E_{v1}	E_{vd}
	(MN/m ²)	(MN/m ²)	(MN/m ²)
Stabilised soil or fly ash	≥ 30	≤ 2,2	≥ 15

In the case of environmental aspects, the Decree-Law n.º UL RS, No. 61/11 requires that the material has to have eluates lower than the leaching limits for the inert waste. Otherwise the waste should be deposited in a landfill. TABLE 32 shows limit values to classify the inert waste.

TABLE 32. LEACHING LIMIT VALUES FOR INERT WASTE

Component	Limit
	Inert waste mg/kg d.s.
As	0,5
Ba	20
Cd	0,04
Cr total	0,5
CU	2
Hg	0,01
Mo	0,5
Ni	0,4
Pb	0,5
Sb	0,06
Se	0,1
Zn	4
Chloride	800
Fluoride	10
Sulphate	1000

Before using the material, it is necessary to perform a test field according to the TSC 06.740 (procedure for building test fields).

2.3.1 Recycling potential analyses for back-fill material

Material MUDIPEL, which was used as the back-fill material behind the retaining wall, could be recycled as a back-fill material or material for the embankment construction. Again, the STS for the second use has to be granted. It is possible to use crushed Mudipel or composite of crushed Mudipel mixed with other soil material. For the back-fill material the soil has to have plastic limit (w_p) lower than 35 %.

Additionally, the following laboratory control tests will be applied for the material quality control (TABLE 33).

TABLE 33. CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL QUALITY CONTROL WITH LABORATORY TESTS.

Description of test	Relevant standard
Determination of water content:	SIST-TS CEN ISO/TS 17892-1:2004
Determination of density	SIST-TS CEN ISO/TS 17892-2:2004
Determination of particle density	SIST-TS CEN ISO/TS 17892-3:2004
Determination of compressive strength	BS 1377: Part 7: Point 7: 1990
Proctor compaction	SIST EN 13286-2:2010

In addition, the on the construction site, the compaction of the material has to be tested with several In-situ tests (TABLE 33):

TABLE 34. CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL QUALITY CONTROL WITH IN-SITU TESTS.

Description of test	Relevant standard
Determination of water content:	TSC 06.711
Determination of density	TSC 06.711
Dynamic modulus	TSC 06.720
Static modulus	TSC 06.720

*TSC; (Slovenian technical specification)

Mechanical properties

Because the very good results of the recycled material Mudipel, the next recycling process and use for back-fill material again should be possible (FIGURE 1).

Dry samples of the composite have low water absorption which indicates good water resistance (FIGURE 2).

FIGURE 1. FREEZE/THAW RESISTANCE FOR DIFFERENT CONTENTS OF DPS (DEINKING PAPER SLUDGE)

FIGURE 2. COMPOSITE ADSORPTION

In laboratory we used a sample from small demo field at Vipap facility. Unfortunately, we have only a sample with the compressibility of 85 %, which means that material was not compressed as it was at the Demo 3 in Mirna peč (95 %). Anyway, we used that sample to test the possibility of Mudipel to be used again.

In laboratory sample of Mudipel (85 % compaction) was crushed (FIGURE 3) and then again compacted at the optimal water content. Uniaxial strength of the recompacted sample (FIGURE 4) is almost the same as it is for the intact samples, which indicates that Mudipel has a good potential to be used again as a back-fill material (TABLE 35). It has to be mentioned that the samples of the 95 % compaction or higher has uniaxial strength 200 kPa after 1 day and 1000 kPa after 7 days.

On the recompacted sample the leaching test was performed but the results have not been available yet.

FIGURE 3 CRUSED MUDIPEL

FIGURE 4 RECOMPACTED MUDIPEL AFTER UNIAXIAL TEST

TABLE 35. UNIAXIAL TEST OF CRUSHED MUDIPEL

Test	MUDIPEL No. GD 17/18	
	intact	recompacted
	kPa	kPa
Uniaxial strength	130-150	135

Leaching tests – chemical analyses

When the freezing/thawing test was finished, the sample of Mudipel was tested again for the uniaxial strength. On the broken sample the leaching test was performed. The chemical results showed that the broken Mudipel has no environmental impact (TABLE 36) which means that the material could be used again as the back-fill material.

TABLE 36. RESULTS OF THE LEAKAGE TEST ON THE BROKEN SAMPLE OF MUDIPEL

Component	Limit	MUDIPEL No. GD 96/17	
	Inert waste mg/kg d.s.	mg/l	mg/kg d.s.
As	0,5	<0,002	<0,02
Ba	20	0,52	5,2
Cd	0,04	<0,0005	<0,005
Cr total	0,5	0,0018	0,018
CU	2	0,026	0,26
Hg	0,01	<0,0001	<0,001
Mo	0,5	<0,005	<0,05
Ni	0,4	<0,001	<0,01
Pb	0,5	<0,005	<0,05
Sb	0,06	<0,0006	<0,006
Se	0,1	<0,001	<0,01
Zn	4	<0,01	<0,1
Chloride	800	2,15	21,5
Fluoride	10	0,17	1,7
Sulphate	1000	<1,00	<10,0

Measurements in the piezometers proved that at least 5 m under the retaining wall structure there is no groundwater level. Anyway we did a chemical analyse of the surface water which flew into the piezometric borehole before the construction was started. Also monitoring of water from the drainage system is a part of the monitoring system of the whole structure. The water collects in a lysimeter, from where samples can be taken. The latest results of chemical analysis of water have shown that components are below the limits of the Regulation on the emission of substances and heat in the discharge of waste water into water and public sewage (UR RS No. 98/15) (TABLE 37) . It means that the recycled material in the structure has no (significant) environmental impact.

TABLE 37. RESULTS OF THE CHEMICAL ANALYSE OF WATER IN THE DRAINAGE SYSTEM OF THE RETAINING CONSTRUCTION

Component	Limit (UR RS No. 98/15)	Surface water in piezometer P6 30.8.2018	Water sample No. K 10/17 12.4.2019
	mg/l		
As	0,1	0,00074	0,0019
Ba	5	0,07	0,0080
Cd	0,025	<0,0002	<0,0002
Cr total	0,5	0,0057	0,0031
Cu	0,5	0,00098	0,042
Hg	0,005	<0,0001	<0,0001
Mo	1	0,0013	0,018
Ni	0,5	0,034	0,0011
Pb	0,5	0,00049	0,0005
Sb	0,3	0,00016	0,0039
Se	0,6	0,00035	0,0005
Zn	2	0,1	<0,0005
Chloride	800*	-	5,17
Fluoride	10	<0,0001	0,264
Sulphates	1000*	<0,00005	19

*according to UR RS No. 61/11

2.4 Circular Case 5 - Mining Sector

In circular case 5, a residual material (GLDs) from the pulp industry is used to remediate closed open pit mining sites. The function provided by the GLDs is required at the mining site for an unforeseeable amount of time and is therefore considered as a final storage for these materials. Due to these circumstances' recyclability is not assessed.

This technical solution has been investigated in smaller areas earlier and the results are promising, the cover function as a sealing layer works well and prohibits oxygen and water transportation. Issues related to durability will be addressed in the demo site by following the performance over time with built in oxygen-and water probes. The demo is situated at a site in Garpenberg where all water is collected, cleaned and analysed continuously.

3 Conclusions

Regarding Circular Cases CC1a and CC1b demo pilots there is a clear notion that wastes coming from future demolition of these construction works have a high recyclability potential due to the low amount of incorporated PPI wastes in precast concrete (case 1a) or bituminous mixtures (case 1b). Nevertheless, to assure the recyclability the operation of preparation of future recycled aggregates should also comply to other requirements present in standards specifications like E471 to E474 and E485 (quoted LNEC specifications).

At the same time that recyclability potential analysis of developed products in the circular cases (1A and 1B) was made in this task 4.3., samples are being prepared in the laboratory regarding these demo cases (WP5), in order to be incorporated as recycled aggregates for new precast concrete products or bituminous mixture products. These new samples will be tested in time and compared with standard materials without wastes. This will allow the evaluation with time of the recyclability potential of these materials, comparing at the same time with the analysis done in this task 4.3.

Recycling trials for soil-stabilised layers of Circular Case 2 have shown that there are no changes in terms of soil classification according to the Spanish Road Regulations. An hypothetical excavation of these layers would lead to a material of the same properties as before the WPFA addition. Mechanical tests have proved that the bearing capacity of clayey soils stabilised with WPFA keep their potential. However, minor changes have been detected in the case of the granular material, the maximum dry density slightly decreases after 6 months placed and later excavation so that, a higher dosage of HRB would be needed in case of re-stabilisation of this granular layer.

Additional laboratory tests shows that recyclability potential of the composite MUDIPEL which was used for Circular Case 3 is high and could be again used as the back-fill material for mining pits or other geotechnical structures.

4 References

IP, Specifications: 14.03 – Paving Materials (in Portuguese), 2014.

LNEC, E 471 - Guide for the use of coarse recycled aggregate in concrete, 2009.

LNEC, E 472 Guide for the use the production of recycled hot mix asphalt, 2009.

LNEC, E 473 Guide for the use of recycled aggregates in unbound pavement layers, 2009.

LNEC, E 474 Guide for the use of recycled materials coming from construction and demolition waste in embankment and capping layer of transport infrastructures, 2009.

LNEC, E 483 Guide for the use of recycled aggregates from reclaimed asphalt for unbound road pavement layers, 2016.

LNEC, E 484 Guide for the use of materials resulting from construction and demolition waste in rural and forest roads, 2016

LNEC, E 485 Guide for the use of materials resulting from construction and demolition waste in backfill of trenches, 2016.

